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Research Article

**WOUND HEALING POTENTIAL OF TRICHOSANTHES
DIOICA EXTRACT HERBAL GEL FORMULATION****Abhishek Kumar Tripathi¹, Sarvesh Kumar Singh¹, Madhusudan Gupta¹, Neha Jain¹**¹Faculty of Pharmaceutical Sciences, RKDF University Bhopal, M.P**Abstract:**

Medicinal plants or traditional remedies have been used for infection, disease, and injury over millennia. Humans have learned to identify and transform the botanical resources from the immediate environment, and with the development of trade, as food and medicine from prehistory. A great many of these "ancient" and traditional medical plants have been validated to confer therapeutic benefits, albeit not always in controlled clinical trials. Plant with good antioxidant and antimicrobial potential would prove to be best therapeutic wound healing agent which can accelerate the wound healing process and prevents its complications, thereby improving the quality of life of patients. Based on review of literature medicinal plants were selected which are used in the treatment of wound healing. Tricosanthese Doica is commonly found plant in India and used to treat various diseases.

Key words: Wound healing, Tricosanthese Doica, Excision wound model, Herbal gel

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INTRODUCTION:

Wound healing is a dynamic and highly regulated process consisting of cellular, humoral and molecular mechanisms. The normal cutaneous wound healing process is a temporal process involving a complex series of overlapping events, which can be divided into key stages including: hemorrhage and fibrin clot formation, inflammatory response, reepithelialization, granulation tissue formation, angiogenic response, connective tissue contraction, and remodelling.

Our skin is the key to our survival, sensing the environment, maintaining physicochemical and thermal homeostasis, acting as a reservoir of essential nutrients, providing passive and active defence, and responding to trauma and injury. Maintaining these critical functions requires robust and effective mechanisms to protect it from trauma and insult and to repair and replace critical skin functions when damaged or lost. Humans have been treating their wounds for millennia. Traditional wound management is limited by what is immediately at hand or can be acquired locally, such as water, soil, and plant and animal products, and is frequently complemented with ceremony and ritual as an added measure. For millions of people across Asia, Africa, the Middle East, and Latin America, traditional medicines derived from local plants, animals, and natural products are the mainstay of wound care; for some, it is the only source of wound care [2].

Maintaining homeostasis is critical for the survival of the organism; hence, skin needs and possesses a robust and effective repair mechanism. Cutaneous wound healing is the process by which skin repairs itself following injury caused by surgery, trauma, and burns. Upon injury, a fibrin clot rapidly forms to restore haemostasis. Platelets present in the blood trigger the clotting cascade and secrete several growth factors, initiating wound healing. In the following inflammation phase, neutrophils migrate into the wound site engulfing foreign debris and killing bacteria by phagocytosis and releasing proteolytic enzymes. Coincidentally, blood monocytes infiltrate the injury site and differentiate into macrophages, releasing proteases to debride the wound, and secrete a mixture of bioactive molecules, including transforming growth factor beta 1, that stimulates the migration of fibroblasts and epithelial cells. The proliferation phase usually starts about 3 days after wounding; it involves diverse activities including angiogenesis (by endothelial cells), granulation tissue formation (by fibroblasts), and reepithelialization (by keratinocytes). In this stage, fibroblasts produce a large amount of extracellular matrix (ECM), mainly collagen, to form the granulation tissue which replaces the damaged tissue. Meanwhile, the

keratinocytes migrate, proliferate, differentiate, and re-form a functional epidermis (reepithelialization), closing the lesion and protecting underlying tissues from further trauma. As the wound matures, the characteristic disorganized ECM of granulation tissue is actively remodelled by the dermal fibroblast cell population, whose numbers are progressively reduced through apoptosis. The outcome of wound healing is scar tissue (fibrosis) with sparsely distributed fibroblasts within a collagen-rich ECM. Compared to the original tissue, scar tissue, having distinct texture and reduced biomechanical and functional properties, is characteristically altered [3-6].

Trichosanthes dioica Roxb. is known by a common name of *parwal* (Pointed gourd) and is cultivated mainly as a vegetable. It is an easily available common plant, the fruit of which is integral part of an average Indian diet, being consumed as a vegetable. Apart from old traditional texts, such as Charak Samhita mentioned the protective role of *Trichosanthes* on important body organs such as liver, spleen, heart, etc., many of which are now scientifically proven. Clinical investigation on peptic ulcer with polyherbal formulation, where *Trichosanthes* was an integral part, has shown promising results. *Trichosanthes* may play a significant role in developing formulations for geriatric care as it is having almost all the properties of pharmaceutical care designed for the elderly, i.e., antioxidant property, antidiabetic property, cholesterol lowering, hepatoprotective, etc. Pointed gourd (*T. dioica*) is known by the name of *parwal*, *palwal*, *parmal*, *patol*, and *potala* in different parts of India and Bangladesh and is one of the important vegetables of this region. The fruits and leaves are the edible parts of the plant which are cooked in various ways either alone or in combination with other vegetables or meats [7]. Wound healing, as a normal biological process in the human body, It is the process of repair that follows injury to the skin and other soft tissues. Wounds that exhibit impaired healing, including delayed acute wounds and chronic wounds, generally have failed to progress through the normal stages of healing. Such wounds frequently enter a state of pathologic inflammation due to a postponed, incomplete, or uncoordinated healing process. Most chronic wounds are ulcers that are associated with ischemia, diabetes mellitus, venous stasis disease, or pressure. Many plants contain phenolic components such as tannins and flavonoids in considerable proportion. These phenolic components are known to have antioxidant and antimicrobial properties and have potential to scavenge free radicals. Oxidative stress resulting from excess of free radicals is one of the major etiological factors for development of chronic

wound and its complications, especially in chronic wound. Exposure of subcutaneous tissue following wound provides a moist, warm, and nutritionally rich environment that favors microbial colonization and proliferation. Since colonization most frequently occurs by a group of potential pathogenic microbes, any wound is at some risk of infection. The development of such wound infection negatively impacts the wound healing process, delaying healing. Topical antimicrobial therapy is one of the most important methods of wound care. Hence, external application of compounds may prevent the microbes to invade through the wound and protects the wound against infection [8-12]. Thus, plant with good antioxidant and antimicrobial potential would prove to be best therapeutic wound healing agent which can accelerate the wound healing process and prevents its complications, thereby improving the quality of life of patients. Based on review of literature medicinal plants were selected which are used in the treatment of wound healing. Tricosanthese Doica is commonly found plant in India and used to treat various diseases.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

Procurement and Authentication of Plant material (*Trichosanthes dioica*): A systematic approach is necessary in pharmacognostic study, which helps in confirmation and determination of identity, purity and quality of a crude drug. Hibiscus rosa-sinensis Linn flowers were collected from Fresh and fully grown plants from the near places of Bhopal, India. *Trichosanthes dioica* fully grown fruits were purchased from local market of Bhopal. Fresh fruits of *Trichosanthes dioica* were used for Pharmacognostical studies. fruits of

Trichosanthes dioica were dried under shade separately. fruits of *Trichosanthes dioica* were powdered to 60# separately and stored in airtight containers and used for phytochemical and pharmacological studies. The Leaves were initially separated from the main plants body and rinsed with distilled water and shade dried and then homogenized into fine powder and stored in air tight bottles.

Macroscopical study: The macroscopical description of fruits of *Trichosanthes dioica* include size, shape, nature of outer and inner surfaces, types of fracture, and organoleptic characters like color, odour, taste etc. were studied.

Preparation of gel containing plant extract formulation: The gel containing plant extract formulation was prepared with methanolic and aqueous extract of T. Diocia mixed in best optimized gel base (G4) to get gel and evaluated as parameters. The quantities of gel ingredients showed in Table 5.2 Methyl paraben sodium (50 mg), Glycerine (5 ml), polyethylene glycol (1 ml) were dissolved in about 25 ml of water in beaker. The dissolved mucilaginous materials were stirred at high speed using mechanical stirrer. Then Carbopol 934 (1 g) and PVP (25 mg) were added slowly to the beaker containing above mixture liquid dispersion while stirring. The gel solution containing plant extract was added with triethanolamine (1 ml) act as gelling agents slowly while stirring to attain translucent gel structure with maximum viscosity. The plant extract gel was finally transferred in aluminium collapsible tube and labelled.

Table 1: Formulae preparation of gel with plant extract

Formulation	Plant extract content
TMG1	Methanolic extract of <i>Trichosanthes dioica</i> fruit (TDME 5 %)
TMG2	Methanolic extract of <i>Trichosanthes dioica</i> fruit (TDME 10 %)
TWG3	Aqueous extract of <i>Trichosanthes dioica</i> fruit (TDWE 5 %)
TWG4	Aqueous extract of <i>Trichosanthes dioica</i> fruit (TDWE 10 %)

Table 2: Formulae preparation of gel with plant extract

Formulation	Carbopol 934 (g)	PVP (mg)	Methyl paraben Sodium (mg)	Glycerine (ml)	PEG (ml)	Triethanolamine (ml)
TMG1	1	25	50	5	1	1
TMG2	1	25	50	5	1	1
TWG3	1	25	50	5	1	1
TWG4	1	25	50	5	1	1

Evaluation of base gel formulation:

Physical appearance: The physical appearance of prepared gel base was visually checked as parameters i.e. colour, appearance and feel on application.

pH determination: The pH of gel base were determined by using the digital pH meter. 0.5 gram of gel base was dissolved in 20 ml distilled water and stored for two hours. pH electrodes were completely dipped into the formulations and pH was noted. The measurement of pH of each formulation was done in triplicate manner and average values were calculated.

Extrudability determination: The gel base was filled into collapsible metal tubes. The tubes were pressed with same pressure by using fingers and the extrudability of the formulations was checked. The extrudability of the formulation was determined in terms of weight in grams required to extrude a 0.5 cm ribbon of gel in 10 seconds.

Viscosity determination: The viscosity of the prepared gel base was measured by Brook field viscometer. The sufficient quantity of gel base was filled in wide mouth jar separately and it should sufficiently allow dipping the spindle. The RPM of the spindle was adjusted to 2.5 RPM. The viscosities of the formulations were recorded.

Spreadability: Spreadability means the extent of area to which gel readily spreads on application to skin or affected part of skin. The therapeutic potency of a formulation also depends upon its spreading value. Spreadability of formulation is expressed in terms of time in seconds taken by two slides to slip off from gel base, which is placed in between the slides under the direction of certain load.

Lesser the time taken for the separation of two slides, better the spreadability. It is calculated by using the formula

$$S = M * L / T$$

where, M = Weight tied to upper slide

L = Length of glass slide

T = Time taken to separate the slides

Homogeneity: The gel base formulations have been set in the container; all prepared gels were tested for homogeneity by visual inspection. They were tested for their appearance and presence of any lumps, flocculates or aggregates.

Grittiness: The gel base formulations were evaluated microscopically for the presence of any appreciable particulate matter under light microscope. The preparation should free from particles and the grittiness of any topical preparation can check.

Pharmacological screening:

Animals: Wistar albino rats (180-220g) of either sex were used for experimental study. The animals were housed in cages at $25 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$, and relative humidity ($50 \pm 5\%$) with 12 h light, and 12 h dark cycle. All the animals were acclimatized to laboratory environment for a week before the experiment. They were provided with free access to food and water ad libitum. The animals were cared and used in accordance with the CPCSEA guidelines.

Wound healing activity:

Preparation of formulations: The ointment of plant extracts were prepared to evaluate its efficacy with ointment base or vehicle for local activity of wound healing. Ointment base was prepared by boiling in a beaker at 65°C water bath using wool fat 5 g, cetostearyl alcohol 5 g and soft white paraffin 90 g as the ingredients. The plant extract (5 g and 10 g) was incorporated in 100 g of the base. Povidone marketed preparation obtained from bhopal was used as standard drug for comparing the wound healing potential of extract in different animal models.

Group of animals: The excision, incision and dead space wound models were used to evaluate the wound-healing activity of methanol and water extract of Herbal ointment formulation. The wistar rats were divided into various groups, each group containing six animals, for excision and incision wound models. 5% and 10% extract containing formulated ointments were applied topically to each animal once a day.

Group I: The animals of received ointment base (control)

Group II: Treated group with a marketed povidone formulation

Group III: Methanolic extract of *Trichosanthes dioica* fruit (TDME 5 %) ointment

Group IV: Methanolic extract of *Trichosanthes dioica* fruit (TDME 10 %) ointment

Group V: Aqueous extract of *Trichosanthes dioica* fruit (TDWE 5 %) ointment

Group VI: Aqueous extract of *Trichosanthes dioica* fruit (TDWE 10 %) ointment

Excision wound model: The animals were divided into three groups with six in each were anaesthetized by open mask method with anesthetic ether before wound creation. The particular skin area was shaved 1 day prior to the experiment. An excision wound was inflicted by cutting away a 300 mm² full thickness of skin from a predetermined shaved area. The wounds were left undressed to the open environment. The ointment base, standard drug ointment (0.1% silver sulfadiazine) and methanolic extract of TDR ointment (5%, w/w) was applied topically to the control group, standard

group and treated group respectively, till the wound was completely healed. In this model, wound contraction and epithelialization period was monitored. Wound contraction was measured as percent contraction in each 2 days after wound formation. From the healed wound, a specimen sample of tissue was collected from each rat for histopathological examination.

Incision wound model: In incision wound model all the animals of each group were anaesthetized under light ether anesthesia. Two full thickness paravertebral long incisions were made through the skin at the distance of about 1 cm from midline on each side of the depilated back of rat. After the incision was made the both edges of skin kept together and stitched with black silk surgical thread (no. 000) and a curved needle (no. 11) was used for stitching. The continuous threads on both wound edges were tightened for good closure of the wound. After stitching, wound was left undressed then ointment base, standard ointment and extracts ointment were applied daily up to 10 days; when wounds were cured thoroughly the sutures were removed on the day 10 and tensile strength of cured wound skin was measured using tensiometer.

Wound healing evaluation parameters

Measurement of wound contraction: An excision wound margin was traced by following the progressive changes in wound area planimetrically, excluding the day of wounding. The size of wounds was traced on a transparent paper in every 2 days, throughout the monitoring period. The tracing was then shifted to graph paper, from which the wound surface area was evaluated. The evaluated surface area was then employed to calculate the percentage of wound contraction, taking initial size of wound, 300 mm², as 100%, by using the following formula as % wound contraction = $\frac{\text{initial wound size} - \text{specific day wound size}}{\text{initial wound size}} \times 100$

Epithelialization period: It was evaluated by noting the number of days required for the Escher to fall off from the wound surface exclusive of leaving a raw wound behind.

Measurement of tensile strength: The force required to open the healing action is known as tensile strength. It is used to measure the completeness of healing. It also indicates how much the repaired tissue resists to breaking under tension and may indicate in part the quality of repaired tissue. The sutures were removed on the 9th day after wounding and the tensile strength was measured on 10th day. For this purpose, the newly formed tissue including scar was excised and tensile strength was measured with the help of tensiometer. In this method, wound-breaking

strength was measured as the weight of water at the time of wound breaking per area of the specimen.

Hydroxyproline estimation: Hydroxyproline is an uncommon amino acid present in the collagen fibres of granulation tissues. Its estimation helps clinically to understand progress rate at which the healing process is going on in the connective tissue of the wound. For the determination of hydroxyproline content, the wound tissues were excised and dried in a hot air oven at 60–70 °C to constant weight and were hydrolysed in 6N HCl at 130 °C for 4 h in sealed glass tubes. The hydrolysate was neutralized to pH 7.0 and was subjected to Chloramine-T oxidation for 20 min. The reaction was terminated by addition of 0.4 M perchloric acid and color was developed with the help of Ehrlich reagent at 60 °C. The absorbance was measured at 557 nm using a spectrophotometer. The amount of hydroxyproline in the samples was calculated using a standard curve prepared with pure l-hydroxyproline

RESULT AND DISCUSSION:

Pharmacognostic study

Procurement and Authentication of Plant material (*Trichosanthes dioica*): Pharmacognostic study helps in confirmation and determination of identity, purity and quality of a plant drug. *Trichosanthes dioica* plant is a perennial, dioecious, and grows as a creeper. Vines of *Trichosanthes dioica* or parval are thin in size having dark green cordate, rigid, leaves. The fruits of *Trichosanthes dioica* are green with white stripes. Fruits are oblong in shape and Size can vary from 6 to 12 cm long.

Figure 1: Morphological evaluation of *Trichosanthes dioica*

Pharmacological screening:

Acute toxicity studies of *Trichosanthes dioica* extracts as per OECD guideline: The objective of this Acute Toxicity Study of *Trichosanthes dioica* on rats was to assess the toxicological profile of the test drug when given orally once (single dose) to the test system (rats) and monitor the vital signs for 14 days. This study will provide information on the possible health hazards likely to arise from single oral exposure of the aqueous and methanol extracts of the plant. The treated animals did not demonstrate any significant changes in behavioral

pattern and exhibited normal activity. Also there were no clinical signs of tremors, convulsions, exophthalmos, salivation, diarrhea and lethargy. There was no significant difference in the mean body weights between treated groups and control group and the rats exhibited normal body weight gain during the study. No lethal effects or mortality

was observed in animals throughout the test period following single oral administration at all selected dose levels of all extracts. The animals were examined for long term toxicity (14 days).

Wound healing activity:

Excision wound model

Table 3: Effect of T. Diocia gel formulation on % of wound contraction of excision wound models in rats

Group	0 Days	3 Days	6 Days	9 Days	12 Days	15 Days	18 Days	21 Days	24 Days
Group I	0	27.34	34.28	47.64	51.4	75.15	86.43	94.76	100
Group II	0	52.24	74.32	99.15	100				
Group III	0	21.14	41.24	61.02	69.24	78.17	98.24	100	
Group IV	0	47.68	68.61	81.41	99.82	100			
Group V	0	18.33	38.12	54.03	63.36	69.21	90.11	98.21	100
Group VI	0	29.47	48.14	69.74	79.14	99.47	100		

Wound contraction: A better healing pattern with complete wound closure was observed in standard and treated group within 10 and 12 days respectively while it was about 24 days in control rats. Group IV treated with methanolic extract of Tricosanthese Doica (10%) showed complete wound closer in 12 days. The result concluded that methanolic extract of Tricosanthese Doica (10%) showed best effect than other extract and significant with treated group.

Table 4: Effect of plant extract ointment on Epithelialization time of excision wound model in rats

Group	Epithelialization time (Days)
Group I	22
Group II	10
Group III	18
Group IV	12
Group V	20
Group VI	15

Epithelialization period: The epithelialization time was measured from the first day. The epithelialization time was found to be significantly ($P < 0.01$) reduced in Groups II and IV. The treatments with methanolic extract of Tricosanthese Doica received ointment base. (10%) showed complete epithilaztion process within 12 days The result concluded that methanolic extract of Tricosanthese Doica (10%) showed best effect than other extract and significant with treated group.

Table 5: Effect of T. Diocia gel fromulation on Hydroxyproline on incision wound model in rats

Group	Hydroxyproline (mg/g tissue)
Group I	23.11 ± 0.001
Group II	70.22 ± 0.002
Group III	41.02 ± 0.002
Group IV	60.13 ± 0.001
Group V	31.13 ± 0.002
Group VI	51.02 ± 0.001

Hydroxyproline content: Treated group showed significant increase in hydroxyproline content when compared to control group ($P < 0.01$). The Hydroxyproline content in incision model estimated at Group IV result was showed 60.13 ± 0.001 (mg/g tissue), which was best result other extract and significant with treated group. In

the case of The Hydroxyproline content in dead space wound model estimated at Group IV result was showed 58.93 ± 0.001 (mg/g tissue), which was best result other extract and significant with treated group.

Table 6: Effect of T. Diocia gel fromulation on Tensile strength on incision wound model in rats

Group	Tensile strength (g/mm ²)
Group I	391.21 \pm 4.21
Group II	595.04 \pm 3.01
Group III	457.31 \pm 3.01
Group IV	515.21 \pm 3.17
Group V	441.32 \pm 2.31
Group VI	481.34 \pm 3.01

Tensile strength: Tensile strength for the treated group on 10th day was found to be significant ($P < 0.01$) than control group. The Tensile strength of incision model estimated at Group IV was 515.21 ± 3.17 (g/mm²), which was best result other extract and significant with treated group. The result concluded that methanolic extract of Tricosanthese Doica (10%) showed best effect than other extract and significant with treated group. In the case of Tensile strength on dead space wound model estimated at Group IV result was showed 510.11 ± 2.26 (mg/g tissue), which was best result other extract and significant with treated group.

CONCLUSION:

Plant and plant products have been utilized with varying success to cure and prevent diseases throughout history. Crude extract mixtures of plant are better than pure isolated chemicals. Several biologically active compounds in a plant work together to produce greater effect than single chemical on its own. Wound healing, as a normal biological process in the human body, It is the process of repair that follows injury to the skin and other soft tissues. Wounds that exhibit impaired healing, including delayed acute wounds and chronic wounds, generally have failed to progress through the normal stages of healing. Such wounds frequently enter a state of pathologic inflammation due to a postponed, incomplete, or uncoordinated healing process. Most chronic wounds are ulcers that are associated with ischemia, diabetes mellitus, venous stasis disease, or pressure. Based on review of literature medicinal plants were selected which is used in the treatment of wound healing. Tricosanthese Doica is commonly found plant in India and used to treat various diseases. In present work Tricosanthese Doica were selected for wound healing activity in animal model. A better healing pattern with complete wound closure was observed in standard and treated group within 10 and 12 days respectively while it was about 24 days in control rats. Group treated with methanolic extract of Tricosanthese Doica (10%) showed complete wound closer in 12 days. The result concluded that methanolic extract of Tricosanthese Doica (10%)

showed best effect than other extract and significant with treated group.

REFERENCES:

1. Reinke, J. M., and Sorg, H. (2012). Wound repair and regeneration. *Eur. Surg. Res.* 49, 35–43. doi: 10.1159/000339613
2. Shedoeva A, Leavesley D, Upton Z, Fan C Wound Healing and the Use of Medicinal Plants; Evidence-Based Complementary and Alternative Medicine Volume 2019, Article ID 2684108, 30 pages
3. Talbott J H, "A short history of medicine," *JAMA*, vol. 180, no. 9, p. 794, 1962.
4. WHO Traditional Medicine Strategy: 2014–2023, ISBN: 97892 41506090.
5. Golebiewska E. M., Poole A. W, "Platelet secretion: from haemostasis to wound healing and beyond," *Blood Reviews*, vol. 29, no. 3, pp. 153–162, 2015.
6. Enoch S, Leaper D. J., "Basic science of wound healing," *Surgery (Oxford)*, vol. 26, no. 2, pp. 31–37, 2008
7. Budovsky A, Yarmolinsky L, and S. Ben-Shabat, "Effect of medicinal plants on wound healing," *Wound Repair and Regeneration*, vol. 23, no. 2, pp. 171–183, 2015.
8. Schreml S, Szeimies RM, L. Prantl, M. Landthaler, and P. Babilas, "Wound healing in the 21st century," *Journal of the American Academy of Dermatology*, vol. 63, no. 5, pp. 866–881, 2010.
9. Wright JA, Richards T, Srari SKS; The role of iron in the skin and cutaneous wound healing, *Frontiers in Pharmacology* July 2014, Volume 5, Article 156, 1
10. Polefka, T. G., Bianchini, R. J., and Shapiro, S. (2012). Interaction of mineral salts with the skin: a literature survey. *Int. J. Cosmet. Sci.* 34, 416–423.
11. Yadav, N., Barman, K., Pal, A. K., Kanaujia, A., Belwal, P., Baite, N. A., & Dadrwal, B. K. (2025). Modulating Antioxidant Capacity and Preserving Chlorophyll Levels in Pointed Gourd (*Trichosanthes dioica* Roxb.) through Synergistic Application of 6-Benzylaminopurine and Sodium Alginate

- Coating during Ambient Storage. Journal of Scientific Research and Reports, 31(5), 38-52.
12. Singh, K., Kumari, M., Chauhan, A. K., Singh, S. V., Pojić, M., & Prakash, S. (2024).

Preparation of petha from pointed gourd (*Trichosanthes dioica*) mediated by osmotic dehydration and its characterization. Journal of Food Science and Technology, 1-9.